

Can the irisin levels in blood circulation on association with feeding habits in *Mastacembelus mastacembelus* and *Cyprinion macrostomus*

 Mustafa Koyun^c

^a Bingöl University, Vocational School of Food, Agriculture and Livestock, Department of Veterinary Medicine, 12000-Bingöl, Türkiye

^b Van Yüziüncü Yıl University, Faculty of Medicine, 23119-Van, Türkiye

^c Bilecik Şeyh Edebali University, Faculty of Science, Department of Molecular Biology and Genetic, 11100-Bilecik, Türkiye

Abstract: Irisin is a peptide that is effective in regulating dietary habits, food intake, body weight, and glucose balance. There is limited research on the irisin hormone in freshwater fish. This research aimed to investigate the serum irisin levels in an omnivorous fish of *C. macrostomus* (*Cyprinion macrostomus*) and a carnivorous fish of *M. mastacembelus* (*Mastacembelus mastacembelus*). Hormone levels were measured using the ELISA (Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay) method. The serum level of irisin hormone was analyzed using the ELISA kit (Phoenix Pharmaceuticals Inc., Burlingame, CA, USA). The results were compared between the two species and between the sexes of each species. Additionally, the levels of iris were compared with the body weight and length of both *M. mastacembelus* and *C. macrostomus*. The adult *C. macrostomus* (n=22) showed lower irisin levels than the adult *M. mastacembelus* (n=22) in both of male and female fish. Serum irisin level was higher in *M. mastacembelus* (1127 ± 71.6 ng/mL), which was fed predominantly carnivores and had large muscle mass, than *C. macrostomus* (513 ± 27.1 ng/mL), which was fed omnivores and had low muscle mass. We conclusion that irisin levels may vary depending on the feeding habits and weight of the fish.

Keywords: Irisin, Feeding habits, *C. macrostomus*, *M. mastacembelus*, Elisa

1. INTRODUCTION

The regulation of energy homeostasis, feeding behaviors, and food intake in fish species is based on the interaction of the central and peripheral pathways (i.e. brain, mostly hypothalamus and endocrinal tissues such as liver and intestines as a response to the energy balance between requirement and availability (Gorissen et al., 2006). The molecules synthesized by hypothalamus play a role in the habitual regulation of feeding (Bulc et al., 2013). Feeding is closely related to food intake and there are central and peripheral homeostatic metabolism including hormones and metabolites to different environmental factors in such a complicated process (Volkoff & Peter, 2006). Recent studies have shown that orexigenic or anorexigenic endocrine signals can stimulate or inhibit peptide hormones that affect food intake (Gorissen et al., 2006; Volkoff et al., 2009). Furthermore, the regulatory mechanisms of appetite and food intake have in recent decade attracted many researchers and the advent of circulating peptide ghrelin has provided much evidence on homeostatic systems regulating food intake and body weight (van der Lely et al., 2004; Vriese De & Delporte, 2008). New stimulants responsible for energy regulation and feeding are being explored for a better understanding of the functions of living systems, and newly discovered hormones have rapidly increased our knowledge about energy balance (İnci & Ünübol Aypak, 2016). Irisin, a 12-kDa thermogenic glycoprotein composed of 112 amino acids not only exists in peripheral tissues such as adipose tissue, pancreas, muscles, and gastrointestinal tract but also affects different areas of the hypothalamus (Boström et al., 2012).

Irisin is a multifunctional endocrine factor in mammals (Polyzos et al., 2005). For example, Irisin has 100% the same structure in humans and mice (Boström et al., 2012). It has been widely examined in almost all tissues in chickens, including brain, adipose tissue, and muscles and FNDC5 is orthologous in chickens (Li et al., 2015). It has also been detected in many avian species (e.g. turkey, duck, zebra finch, and penguin) and rats as well as several reptiles such as anole lizards, *Xenopus tropicalis* (Varela-Rodriguez et al., 2016). Further, the coelacanth and zebrafish have irisin mostly in their brains (Li et al., 2015), and rarely in peripheral tissues such as tilapia (Lian et al., 2017).

The role of irisin hormone which is mostly secreted by muscle cells, on regulation of food intake and energy homeostasis in mammals (Zhang & Zhang 2016; Butt et al., 2017; Sundarajan & Unniappan, 2017). However, this hormone has not been studied much in fish. It has been observed in all of the examined vertebrates that the transmembrane domain and cytoplasmic extension of FNDC5 is significantly conserved. Its genuine nature can be identified thanks to researches on the structure of FNDC5/irisin, whereas our knowledge is very limited regarding the structure, expression, and roles of FNDC5 and the irisin-coded product in non-mammalian vertebrates (Li et al., 2015).

Fish of the Mastacembelidae family have spread to freshwater environments, the only species of this family in Türkiye is *Mastacembelus mastacembelus*, which has spread into the Tigris, Euphrates, and Orontes river systems. The fish's full-length jaw teeth indicate its carnivorous eating habits (Geldiay & Balık, 1996; Dağlı & Erdemli, 2009; Koyun et al., 2023). Food perception and diet composition can determine feeding habits of fish species (Carr et al., 1996). It is assumed that the diet of *M. mastacembelus* includes invertebrates because a study reported that the fish eats skeletal fish remains and eggs and young of other fish species in its diet (Coad, 2015). *M. mastacembelus* preys mainly on shrimp (55%) and fish (45%) (Hussain et al., 2008), The gut contents of specimens from Türkiye included plant material, cladocerans, copepods, and fish (Pala et al., 2010). Valenzuela et al., (1995) suggest that the presence of phytoplankton in the gut contents may account for the ingestion of zooplankton that have fed on phytoplankton, or copepod fecal pellets.

C. macrostomus, an edible fish species, is valuable in sport fishing and also called "doctor fish" because it is used for certain medical treatments. Such an omnivorous species feeds on phytoplanktons and zooplankton (Ündar et al., 1990; Kırıcı et al., 2022; Caf et al., 2023; Şen Özdemir et al., 2023). Khan (1988) reported that many factors indicate the herbivorous feeding habits of this fish, including the long gut, absent stomach, gills for filtration of food particles, absent tongue, depressed buccal cavity, and absent teeth as well as its gut contents of mostly plant material (including green algae, diatoms, blue-green algae, desmids, and phytoflagellates) and decayed organic matter.

Various functions of FNDC5/irisin have been investigated in mammals (Polyzos et al., 2005; Boström et al., 2012; Li et al., 2015). However, our knowledge is limited on the irisin hormone in non-mammalian vertebrates like fish. There are extensive studies conducted to investigate how organisms protect their energy balance and collect data on food intake. However, the researches on irisin have all been laboratory-oriented, that's there is no field study. We aimed to examine and identify the serum irisin levels in *C. macrostomus* and *M. mastacembelus*, depending on dietary intake.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

Adult *C. macrostomus* (14 females, 8 males) and adult *M. mastacembelus* (10 females, 12 males) were obtained from Murat Lake (Elazığ-Bingöl, Türkiye). The study was designed and started with the approval dated 2015 March 27 and numbered 2015/02-01/02 given by the Animal Experiments Local Ethics Board of Bingöl University. The sample fish were anesthetized with 0.05% Tricaine methanesulfonate and separated by sex. The length (cm) and weight (g) of each *M. mastacembelus* and *C. macrostomus* were measured. Blood samples (3–5 ml) were taken from the caudal vein and introduced into tubes containing aprotinin to prevent protein denaturation. The clot formation was followed by centrifugation, and the serum samples were stored at -70°C before hormone

measurements were performed (Hettich, Zentrifugen Universal 32 R, Germany). Irisin was determined using ELISA kits with a sensitivity of 0.78 ng/mL (Phoenix Pharmaceuticals Inc., Burlingame, CA, USA). The intra-assay coefficient of variation and sensitivity for irisin was computed as 5.61%, and the inter-assay coefficient as 14.56%. The plates were read at 450 nm with a SpectraMax Plus384 plate reader.

2.1. Statistical analysis

The results are expressed as mean \pm SEM. The data were normally distributed according to the Kolmogorov–Smirnov Z-test. The unpaired t-test was used for inter-group analysis, and the paired t-test for intra-group statistics by sex. The significance level was considered $p < .05$. Pearson's correlation coefficient determined the interaction of irisin levels and the mean length and weight of the sample species.

3. RESULTS

The length and weight were on average 17.6 ± 0.3 cm and 67.7 ± 3.0 g in the omnivorous *C. macrostomus* and 50.5 ± 2.2 cm and 283.1 ± 37.2 g in the carnivorous *M. mastacembelus*.

Figure 1. The serum irisin levels for each individual fish in *C. macrostomus* group and in *M. mastacembelus* group.

The serum irisin levels for each individual fish are presented in Figure 1. The mean (\pm SEM) serum irisin levels were found to be significantly ($p < 0.0001$) lower in *C. macrostomus* (513 ± 27.1 ng/mL) compared to *M. mastacembelus* (1127 ± 71.6 ng/mL), (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Irisin in the blood serum of *C. macrostomus* ($n = 22$) and *M. mastacembelus* ($n = 22$) (mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.0001$). * represent statistically significance differences.

There was a statistically significant difference between the sexes in *C. macrostomus*, with irisin levels of 435 ± 51.7 ng/mL in the males and 558 ± 24.9 ng/mL in the females ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 3). However, irisin levels were not significantly different between the *M. mastacembelus* males and females (1167 ± 111.6 ng/mL versus 1079.4 ± 87.0 ng/mL, respectively, $p > 0.05$) (Figure 4). Overall, the serum irisin levels in both female and male *C. macrostomus* was significantly lower than in *M. mastacembelus* ($p < 0.0001$) (Figure 5, 6).

Figure 3. Irisin levels in the blood serum of male ($n = 8$) and female ($n = 14$) of *C. macrostomus* (mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$). * represent statistically significance differences.

Figure 4. Irisin levels in the blood serum of male (n = 12) and female (n = 10) of *M. mastacembelus* (mean \pm SEM, $p > 0.05$).

Figure 5. Irisin levels in the blood serum of female *C. macrostomus* (n = 14) and *M. Mastacembelus* (n = 10) (mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$).
* Represent statistically significance differences.

Figure 6. Irisin levels in the blood serum of male *C. macrostomus* (n = 8) and *M. mastacembelus* (n = 12) (mean \pm SEM, $p < 0.05$).
* Represent statistically significance differences.

No significant correlation was observed between serum irisin levels and body weight ($r=0.161$, $p=0.473$ and $r=-0.248$, $p=0.266$) or length ($r=0.042$, $p=0.851$ and

$r=-0.148$, $p=0.512$) in the sample species *C. macrostomus* and *M. mastacembelus*, respectively.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In this study, the presence of irisin in the blood/serum of *C. macrostomus* (513 ± 27.1 ng/mL) and *M. mastacembelus* (1127 ± 71.6 ng/mL) was determined. The length and weight were on average 17.6 ± 0.3 cm and 67.7 ± 3.0 g in the omnivorous *C. macrostomus* and 50.5 ± 2.2 cm and 283.1 ± 37.2 g in the carnivorous *M. mastacembelus*.

Irisin has primarily been detected and studied in plasma, serum, and skeletal muscle, but it has also been found in adipose tissue, liver, kidney, lungs, cerebrospinal fluid, breast milk, and saliva. In this study, the irisin hormone was determined in serum.

The irisin expression was detected in all of the examined tissues of tilapia, including optic tectum, spinal cord, telencephalon, hypothalamus, medulla oblongata, pituitary gland, liver, and muscle, and at low levels in the intestine, kidney, spleen, and stomach (Lian et al., 2017).

Wu et al., (2015) reported that intersegmental vessel formations are more likely to occur by human irisin which declines chemically induced blockage in zebrafish. In 2006, Volkoff and Peter emphasized that several peripheral agents could influence food intake in fish, including cholecystokinin (CCK), gastrin-releasing peptide (GRP), ghrelin, glucagon-like peptides, insulin, amylin, and leptin. These factors act as satiety signals to cut down meal size and food intake, except for gastric factor ghrelin Crujeiras et al., (2014) observed that irisin had a direct association with insulin and an inverse correlation with ghrelin, which is a circulating orexigenic hormone reacting to insulin and leptin. Crujeiras et al., (2014) suggested that irisin is one of the related hormones to body-weight homeostasis under the weight-regaining conditions in association with insulin sensitivity and like leptin, a contributing factor in development of insulin resistance. Following a diet, insulin resistance may increase during the weight-maintenance period among patients having higher levels of irisin. Boström's (2012) study showed that while 72% of FNDC5/irisin in the circulation was provided by muscles, the remaining 28% was released from adipose tissue (Roca-Rivada et al., 2013).

Researches on the energy requirement of fish have found that carnivorous fishes have limited use for carbohydrates as an energy source and mostly prefer dietary lipids (Akpınar & Metin, 1999). This is the first study to show that gender has a significant effect on serum irisin levels in *C. macrostomus*. There was a markedly higher irisin levels in females compared to males of the *C. macrostomus* (Figure 3).

İnci & Üñübol Aypakin (2016) reported that the mRNA expression of FNDC5/irisin was analyzed with the help of polymerase chain reaction (PCR). However, the protein expression did not exactly reflect the irisin levels in the

circulation. Elisa is used to identify the circulating irisin levels because this tool kit is economical, is able to carry out measurements even at low concentrations and quickly provides results. Another purpose was to evaluate circulating serum irisin levels with regard to body weight and the feeding habits of *C. macrostomus* and *M. mastacembelus*. In this study were found to be significantly lower in the omnivorous *C. macrostomus* than in the carnivorous *M. mastacembelus* (Figure 2). Such a difference may depend on the applied feeding patterns. Butt et al., (2017) reported that irisin was an anorexigenic factor in fish (*Carassius auratus*), and its effects could be partially intervened by appetite-regulating factors.

In conclusion, we determined that the irisin levels were significantly lower in the omnivorous *C. macrostomus* than in the carnivorous *M. mastacembelus* for both females and males. In the context of the present study, it was considered that the serum irisin concentration was proportionate to the muscle and fat content of fishes. We also took into consideration that high muscle mass of *M. mastacembelus* and hence higher blood irisin levels could be related to its predominantly carnivorous diet.

No correlation was observed between the serum FNDC5/irisin and the weight or length of both species. However, the serum irisin levels varied by species and sex. Tissue localization of hormones and their concentration changes have been previously studied among fish species although there is little knowledge concerning the effect of that hormone on nutrition, or the mechanisms involved. The current outcomes provide evidence for potential effects of FNDC5 or irisin on fish metabolism and may encourage the future researches in this topic.

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Authors' Contributions:

FC: Manuscript design, Field sampling, Draft checking.

SA: Writing, Draft checking, Reading, Editing.

MK: Laboratory experiments, Statistical analyses.

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Statement on the Welfare of Animals

Ethical approval: All applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were followed.

Data Availability Statements

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article.

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